

Conducting a Home Experiment Related to the Colligative Properties of Chemical Solutions.

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Abstract

The experimental part of teaching chemistry in a series of laboratory activities complements the fundamental learning of the various topics covered in a chemistry course. However, alternatives are necessary when situations arise where it is impossible to have a chemistry laboratory. Conducting home experiments can be of great help in teaching various chemistry topics, as they can be used in tasks, research scenarios, and alternative laboratory practices. They can be applied to different levels of teaching depending on their orientation and the contents they address. In the absence of a laboratory to conduct chemistry practice experiments due to Covid-19 faculty and student confinements at home, we developed feasible practices to do at home with ordinary homemade materials that were not risky or dangerous. We selected solutions with desired colligative properties. Thirty engineering students taking two university chemistry laboratory classes participated, coming from programs in the chemical area such as chemical engineering and biotechnology engineering, among others. The teaching-learning process was conducted remotely via Zoom. The students appreciated the in-home practices. Motivated to understand the topics, they performed well on the exams and the laboratory reports and issued high opinions of the classes in the student survey.

Keywords: Concentration, solutions, colligative properties, higher education, educational innovation

1 Introduction

Chemistry courses are part of the curricula of most engineering careers in the various institutions of higher education, such as Tecnológico de Monterrey or the Autonomous Metropolitan University. They are usually composed of theoretical and experimental parts, the latter occurring with practices of specific course topics in a chemistry laboratory.

However, it is not always possible to have a chemistry laboratory for the experimental phase of a chemistry course due to unforeseen (or even foreseen) situations for social, administrative, or medical reasons.

In this case, technological tools such as the Zoom videoconferencing application can facilitate convenient and effective remote teaching when the traditional face-to-face teaching modality is impossible.

Also, laboratory activities can be adapted to take place outside of physical laboratories to meet the objectives of the experimental phase of the chemistry courses. In this study, we sought to work with topics on solutions and their colligative properties, which are taught in chemistry courses at different levels.

2 Theoretical Framework

Conducting experiments related to the colligative properties of solutions to support the theoretical content is part of the chemistry curricula at different academic levels.

The four colligative properties are a) the decrease in the vapor pressure of a liquid (P°), b) the increase in boiling temperature (t_b), c) the decrease in freezing temperature (T_f), and d) osmotic pressure (π). They only depend on the number of solute particles in the solution and not on the nature of the solute particles (Chang, 2002).

This work focused on practices related to the colligative properties of solutions and specifically on increasing boiling temperature (Δt_b) and decreasing freezing temperature (ΔT_f).

Both the increase in boiling temperature and the decrease in the freezing point are proportional to the molal concentration (m) of the solution and an ionization factor " i " (the van't Hoff factor). The proportionality constants are K_b (molal constant of boiling point elevation) and K_f (molal constant of the decrease in freezing point), both with units of $^{\circ}\text{C} / m$. Therefore:

$$\Delta T_b = i K_b m \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta T_f = i K_f m \quad (2)$$

The Van't Hoff factor (i) is related to the solutions that form electrolytes since these dissociate into ions, separating into two or more particles, which are the ones that determine the colligative properties of a solution and can be defined as:

$$i = \frac{\text{Actual Number of particles in the solution after the disassociation}}{\text{Number of moles dissolved initially in the dissolution}}$$

Table 2. Regarding the molal constants of boiling point elevation and the freezing point decrease of several common liquids, both K_b and K_f only depend on the solvent (Chang, 2002)

Solvent	Normal freezing point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	K_f ($^{\circ}\text{C} / m$)	Normal boiling point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	K_b ($^{\circ}\text{C} / m$)
Water	0	1.86	100	0.52
Benzene	5.5	5.12	80.1	2.53
Ethanol	-117-3	1.99	78.4	1.22
Acetic acid	16.6	3.90	117.9	2.93
Cyclohexane	6.6	20,0	80.7	2.79

This implies that in non-electrolytes (covalent solutes), the van t Hoff factor has a value of one. A strong electrolyte such as CaCl_2 will optimally have a value of three because this compound is ionized in a calcium particle Ca^{+2} and two particles of chlorine Cl^{-1} .

Table 3. Van't Hoff factor for 0.05 M electrolyte solutions at 25°C (Chang, 2002)

Electrolyte	i measured	i calculated
Sucrose (is not an electrolyte)	1.0	1.0
HCl	1.9	2.0
NaCl	1.9	2.0
MgSO_4	1.3	2.0
MgCl_2	2.7	3.0
FeCl_3	3.4	4.0

This table presents the values of i , measured experimentally and those calculated assuming a complete dissociation. They are similar. There is no appreciable formation of ionic pairs that do not have a net charge and reduce the number of particles in the solution.

3 Background

The colligative properties experiments and others are covered in a laboratory manual for a chemistry laboratory equipped with the appropriate materials (Serrano, 2020). However, if a physical laboratory is not available, experiments can be conducted virtually (Infante, 2014), (Vega, 2016). Moreover, we contemplated an alternative practice that could be carried out in any home (Zapata, 2020).

Zapata (Zapata 2020) promotes experimenting at home with homemade materials usually found in a kitchen. Although these experiments do not require chemistry laboratory equipment such as beakers and specimens, they require a thermometer to measure the solution's boiling temperatures and freezing points, which is not an instrument usually found in a house. If the home does have a thermometer, it is usually a clinical one, and its temperature measurement range is not sufficient to measure the temperatures involved in experimental practices.

Well (Well, 2004) and Braga (2022) explain that you do not need a laboratory built for specific purposes or a closet with specialized and expensive equipment to perform chemistry experiments. Most can be carried out with simple materials found in the kitchen, the bathroom, and the pharmacy or convenience stores. However, they do not mention an experiment that involves temperature measurement.

4 Proposal for the home laboratory practice

To develop the various course practices, teachers, as far as feasible, can simulate chemistry laboratory experiments and provide tutorial videos from various educational institutions (Chen et al. 2013), (Infante 2014), (Vega et al. 2016) related to the topics to be discussed. These can be available to all on the network. In addition, educators can design no-risk experiments adapted to the program contents to be performed in the students' homes with household materials while maintaining the level of knowledge established by the course objectives.

Considering the difficulty of measuring a solution's boiling and freezing temperatures in a home experiment to teach colligative properties, we looked for a parallel variable proportional to the difference in boiling and freezing temperatures between a pure liquid and a solution formed by it.

Since the solute content in a solution causes it to boil at a higher temperature than the pure solvent, according to equation (1), we contemplated measuring the time the pure solvent boils and the time to boil the solution. This time difference would be proportional to the temperature difference. Thus, using the same solvent and different solutes, it could be deduced which would have higher ΔT_b and, therefore, higher boiling temperature, considering the same molal concentrations in all cases.

For example, suppose an aqueous solution A takes 400 seconds to start boiling, a solution B 450 seconds and water alone 300 seconds. In that case, it could be concluded that solution B has a higher boiling point than solution A and, therefore, a higher ΔT_b , which would constitute a starting point for the student to analyze the observed phenomenon and its implications.

According to equation 2, something similar could be done to determine which solution would have the lowest freezing point and the highest value of ΔT_f . In this case, it would be more complicated to determine the freezing times of the solvent and the solutions used in the experiment.

5 Methodology

The students in two classes of 30 each studying this subject were instructed to mark a glass at a given height above the middle and obtain a small measuring spoon in their house. Otherwise, they could get the lid of a jar as small as possible and three equal soft-drink bottle caps or something similar.

Figure 1.

They were told to fill the glass with tap water to the mark on the glass and place it in another similar glass. The students were then asked to refill the glass with water to the indicated mark, add two sugar measures with the measuring spoon, shake it to dissolve evenly and place the formed solution in another glass. Next, they were instructed to repeat the same procedure but add a measure of salt to the marked glass so that the identical amounts of water, sugar solution, and the saline solution would be in the first, second, and third glasses, respectively.

Figure 2.

The students were then asked to carefully fill a bottle cap with the liquid from each glass and place them in the kitchen freezer, long enough for the solutions to freeze.

Figure 3.

Next, we instructed the students to pour all the contents of the first glass into a pot and place it on a kitchen stove burner to observe how long it took for the water to boil. At the end of the experiment, they emptied the pot, rinsed it, and allowed it and the stove to cool. Then, they were to repeat the same procedure with the solutions in the other two vessels, trying to maintain as much as possible the same process conditions.

Figure 4.

Finally, they were asked to explain and justify what they had obtained and observed during the performance of these home chemical experiments in the laboratory report used in each practice.

6 Results

All the students reported that the time to reach boiling in the saline solution was more than the sugary one, which, in turn, was longer than the pure water. Moreover, the latter was the first to freeze, then the sugar water, and finally the saline solution much later; some even pointed out that the salt solution did not freeze.

75% of them explained that sugar was a covalent compound and that salt was ionic, which was the reason for the difference in the times obtained. 62% correctly contemplated the van t Hoff factor concept. Only 28 % tried to apply specific numerical calculations to justify the experimental process, concluding that more particles were dissolved in the saline solution than in the sugary one.

In a series of interviews, most of the students opined that this activity had awakened their interest in the subject but found it challenging to understand. Something similar happens in problem-based learning or research, even when it involves simple things of daily life.

At the end of the course, all the program topics were analyzed. 81% of the students solved the problem related to colligative properties with a level of difficulty similar to other tasks and exams of various chemistry courses that most students considered too complex to understand.

7 Conclusions

In the absence of laboratories to conduct experimental practices of a chemistry course for any reason, one can turn to virtual technological supports such as simulators and descriptive videos, which are undoubtedly very useful. However, alternative practices with materials commonly used at home can complement these activities so that the student feels the closest possible to the activities and methodology in a laboratory.

All the students liked doing the home-based activities for the level of rapport and presence they felt, unlike watching a descriptive video or tutorial where there could be a certain degree of dispersion at any given moment. The home experiments motivated them to study the subject, investigate, and understand the

observed chemical phenomena; some even proposed that similar home activities be developed in other practices

Conducting chemistry experiments of this type is economical and feasible outside a laboratory's scope. Depending on the teacher's management and approach, they do not detract from the quality or level of knowledge in the significant learning of one or several topics.

While in this case, the work was developed as an educational response to unexpected home confinement for the entire population, including students and university professors, the methodology could also be used in everyday teaching of theoretical chemistry courses.

It would be convenient to continue developing experimental activities of this type for various topics of chemistry courses for the educational benefit that they can entail.

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